

Pre-intervention questionnaire:

My Engagement in Classes Dedicated to Literary Education

This questionnaire, based on the studies of Alrajhi (2020), Csikszentmihalyi (1990), Silva et al. (2016) and Veiga (2014), aims to assess your perceptions of the classes centred on narrative literary works, along with their compatibility with the use of educational Visual Novels. In addition, it intends to collect information about your habits and preferences related to these digital artifacts. The estimated time to complete the questionnaire corresponds to twenty minutes.

There are 11 questions in this questionnaire.

My Engagement in Classes Dedicated to Literary Education

▪ **Cognitive dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
When we do activities on narrative works, I have difficulties in understanding the instructions.							
When I am reading or studying narrative works, I relate them to what I learned in other subjects.							
When I am reading or studying narrative works, I relate them to what I learned from my personal experience.							
My abilities are not enough to perform activities on narrative works.							
I carry out activities on a narrative work autonomously, without significant difficulties.							
When I am reading a narrative work, I have difficulties in understanding what the author intends to convey.							
I have difficulties in assessing my performance in activities.							
I identify the themes and messages present in the works I am studying with ease.							

▪ **Affective dimension** - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I enjoy the classes where we study narrative works.							
I feel challenged in classes centred on narrative works.							
I do not feel capable enough to overcome difficulties related to the study of narrative works.							
My perception of time changes when I do activities centred on narrative texts (time passes more slowly or faster).							
Reading and studying narrative works is an emotional experience for me.							
I am afraid of making mistakes in activities and exercises about narrative works.							
I do not feel rewarded on a personal level when I successfully perform activities centred on narrative works.							
When I read or study a narrative work, I imagine myself experiencing the adventures of the characters.							

▪ **Behavioural dimension** - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I tend to miss or be late to classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I am usually focused during classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I behave during classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I follow the teacher's instructions in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I respect my colleagues when they participate in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I tend to distract my colleagues in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I avoid performing activities or exercises on the works I am studying.							

My actions compromise the flow of classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
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▪ **Agentive dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I fully read the works I am studying, even if it is not requested by the teacher.							
I avoid participating and sharing what I think about the works I am studying.							
I avoid sharing with the teacher what I like and do not like about the activities on the works I am studying.							
I like it when I can choose what Literary Education activities to do.							
I strive to overcome my difficulties and be successful in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I try to be creative and original in the activities that are assigned to me.							
I do not appreciate it when the teacher lets me choose the type of activities to do.							
I dedicate part of my free time to searching for information about the work I am studying, even if the assessment dates are not close.							

My habits, preferences and perceptions related to video games

▪ **Have I ever played narrative video games?**

Please select **only one** of the following options:

- I have never played them and do not intend to play.
- I have never played them, but I would like to play.
- Yes, I played them in the last six months.
- Yes, I played them last year.

▪ **How much time, on average, do I dedicate to playing narrative video games?**

Please select **only one** of the following options:

- None.
- Less than an hour a week.
- Between one and three hours a week.
- Between four and six hours a week.
- More than six hours a week.

▪ **What types of narrative video games do I like to play?**

Please select **all** that apply:

- Simulators.
- Visual Novels – Japanese-inspired video games in the form of interactive books, focused on story, characters and decision-making.
- "Role Player Games" ("RPG") – video games where you take on a character’s role in a fictional setting.
- Adventure and action video games.
- Strategy video games.
- Platform video games.
- None of the above.

▪ **Based on your perception of educational video games, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Educational video games facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and skills.							
Educational video games do not effectively enhance learning.							
Video games can make learning fun and engaging/immersive.							
Video games are not good learning tools, as they promote addiction and/or social isolation.							
Working with educational video games in the classroom promotes creativity and the expression of my individuality.							

Educational video games are not effective because they are targeted at a male audience.							
Using educational video games in the classroom is boring and compromises learning.							
Video games can be educational if their design is appropriate for the established learning goals.							

▪ **Based on your perception of educational narrative video games, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Narrative video games can be used to learn about narrative texts, as both tell a story.							
Using narrative video games in classes centred on narrative works is a boring experience.							
Using narrative video games increases interest in reading the works included in the curriculum.							
Narrative video games are not effective for learning texts of this nature, as they do not capture their literary richness.							
Narrative video games contain aspects (visual, interactive, sound-related) that generate immersion/engagement in learning.							
Narrative video games are not useful for learning about narrative works, because they are too different from literary texts.							
Narrative video games do not facilitate learning about narrative works, as they disrupt and distract.							
Using narrative video games to study narrative works helps to adopt a focused posture in class.							

▪ **Based on your perception of the design of educational video games, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am interested in video game design.							
It is fun to create my own didactic (learning) materials.							

Participating in the design of educational video games is an opportunity to improve my understanding of the works.							
Participating in the design of educational video games increases interest in the narrative works I am studying.							
Creating educational video games is not advantageous for learning, because it is a difficult and time-consuming process.							
Participating in the design of educational video games is a boring experience.							
Designing educational video games in the classroom is an experience that promotes creativity.							
It is rewarding to know that I am responsible for creating a creative and educational digital resource.							

▪ **Based on your perception of group activities, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I prefer to do activities on narrative works in a group, because dividing the tasks among colleagues is advantageous.							
I prefer to do activities on narrative works alone, because I have more control over what I am doing.							
Exchanging ideas with colleagues improves my problem-solving skills.							
Considering different opinions when carrying out activities increases their quality and originality.							
Individual work is faster and more productive, because I do not need to negotiate ideas with others and reach a consensus.							
It is more fun to carry out activities centred on narrative works in a group, with the possibility of interacting and talking with colleagues.							
It is more advantageous to carry out activities on narrative works alone, as I do not run the risk of becoming distracted.							
Working on narrative works in groups is boring and compromises learning.							

Post-intervention questionnaire:

My Engagement in the Co-design of Educational Visual Novels in Classes Dedicated to Literary Education

This questionnaire, "My engagement in the co-design of Visual Novels in classes dedicated to Literary Education", based on the studies of Alrajhi (2020), Csikszentmihalyi (1990), Silva et al. (2016) and Veiga (2014), aims to ascertain your perceptions of the classes aimed at the collaborative design of educational Visual Novels. The estimated time to complete the questionnaire corresponds to twenty minutes.

There are 11 questions in this questionnaire.

My Engagement in Classes Dedicated to Literary Education

▪ **Cognitive dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
When we do activities on narrative works, I have difficulties in understanding the instructions.							
When I am reading or studying narrative works, I relate it to what I learned in other subjects.							
When I am reading or studying narrative works, I relate them to what I have learned from my personal experience.							
My abilities are not enough to perform activities on narrative works.							
I carry out activities on a narrative work autonomously, without significant difficulties.							
When I am reading a narrative work, I have difficulties in understanding what the author intends to convey.							
I have difficulties in assessing my performance in activities.							
I identify the themes and messages present in the works with ease.							

▪ **Affective dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I enjoy the classes where we study narrative works.							
I feel challenged in classes centred on narrative works.							
I do not feel capable enough to overcome difficulties related to the study of narrative works.							
My perception of time changes when I do activities centred on narrative texts (time passes more slowly or faster).							
Reading and studying narrative works is an emotional experience for me.							
I am afraid of making mistakes in activities and exercises about narrative works.							
I do not feel rewarded on a personal level when I successfully perform activities centred on narrative works.							
When I read or study a narrative work, I imagine myself experiencing the adventures of the characters.							

▪ **Behavioural dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I tend to miss or be late to classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I am usually focused during classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I behave during classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I follow the teacher's instructions in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I respect my colleagues when they participate in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							

I tend to distract my colleagues in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I avoid performing activities or exercises on the works I am studying.							
My actions compromise the flow of classes dedicated to Literary Education.							

▪ **Agentive dimension - Based on your perception of your engagement in the classes focused on narrative works, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I fully read the works I am studying, even if it is not requested by the teacher.							
I avoid participating and sharing what I think about the works I am studying.							
I avoid sharing with the teacher what I like and do not like about the activities on the works I am studying.							
I like it when I can choose what Literary Education activities to do.							
I strive to overcome my difficulties and be successful in classes dedicated to Literary Education.							
I try to be creative and original in the activities that are proposed to me.							
I do not appreciate it when the teacher lets me choose the type of activities to do.							
I dedicate part of my free time to reviewing and searching for information about the work I am studying, even if the assessment dates are not close.							

My perceptions about the co-design of educational Visual Novels

▪ **What do I think about educational Visual Novels?**

Please select **only one** of the following options:

- They are fun and good learning tools.
- They are fun, but do not support learning.

- They are boring, but informative and educational.
- They are boring and inefficient in supporting learning.

▪ **Am I thinking of voluntarily playing the video games created in class, in order to deepen my understanding of the work I am studying?**

Please select **only one** of the following options:

- Yes.
- No.

▪ **Based on your perception of educational Visual Novels, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Educational Visual Novels facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and skills.							
Educational Visual Novels do not effectively enhance learning.							
Visual Novels can make learning fun and engaging/immersive.							
Visual Novels are not good learning tools, as they promote addiction and/or social isolation.							
Working with educational Visual Novels in the classroom promotes creativity and the expression of my individuality.							
Educational Visual Novels are not effective, because they are targeted at a male audience.							
Using educational Visual Novels in the classroom is boring and compromises learning.							
Visual Novels can be educational if their design is appropriate for the established learning goals.							

▪ Based on your perception about educational Visual Novels, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Educational Visual Novels help learn about narrative texts, as both tell a story.							
Using educational Visual Novels in classes centred on narrative works is a boring experience.							
Using educational Visual Novels increases interest in reading the works present in the curriculum.							
Educational Visual Novels are not effective for learning texts of this nature, as they do not capture their literary richness.							
Educational Visual Novels contain aspects (visual, interactive, sound-related) that generate immersion/involvement in learning.							
Educational Visual Novels are not useful for learning about narrative works, because they are too different from literary texts.							
Educational Visual Novels do not allow for learning about works of this nature, as they disrupt and distract.							
Using educational Visual Novels to study narrative works helps to adopt a concentrated posture in class.							

▪ Based on your perception about the co-design of educational Visual Novels, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am interested in designing educational Visual Novels.							
It is fun to create my own didactic (learning) materials.							
Participating in the design of educational Visual Novels is an opportunity to improve my understanding of the works.							
Participating in the design of educational Visual Novels increases interest in the narrative works I am studying.							
Creating educational Visual Novels is not advantageous for learning, because it is a difficult and time-consuming process.							
Participating in the design of educational Visual Novels is a boring experience.							

Designing Visual Novels in the classroom is an experience that promotes creativity.							
It is rewarding to know that I am responsible for designing a creative and educational digital resource.							

▪ **Based on your perception about the co-design of educational Visual Novels, indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements, assigning them a score from 1 to 7, where 1 represents "I do not agree" and 7 represents "I strongly agree".**

Please select the appropriate position for each element:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I prefer to create educational Visual Novels in a group, because dividing the tasks among colleagues is advantageous.							
I prefer to create educational Visual Novels alone, because I have more control over what I am doing.							
Exchanging ideas with colleagues, when co-designing educational Visual Novels, increases my problem-solving skills.							
Considering different opinions when co-designing educational Visual Novels increases their quality and originality.							
Creating educational Visual Novels alone is faster and more productive, because I do not need to negotiate ideas with others and reach a consensus.							
It is more fun to participate in the co-design of educational Visual Novels, with the possibility of interacting and talking with colleagues.							
It is more advantageous to design educational Visual Novels alone, as I do not run the risk of becoming distracted.							
Participating in the co-design of educational Visual Novels is boring and compromises learning.							

Non-participant Class Observation Grid

Goal: Collect information on learner engagement in Literary Education, filling in, if possible, the grids below.

		Yes	No
Cognitive dimension	a. Do the students understand the instructions for the activities?		
	b. Do the students relate the work they are studying with their personal experience?		
	c. Do the students relate the work they are studying with what they learned in other subjects?		
	d. Do the students demonstrate a good level of knowledge and abilities?		
	e. Do the students do the activities autonomously, without significant difficulties?		
	f. Do the students reveal a good understanding of the meanings conveyed by the work they are studying?		
	g. Are the students aware of the quality of their performance?		
	h. Do the students identify the themes and messages conveyed by the work they are studying?		

		Yes	No
Affective dimension	a. Do the students show interest in class?		
	b. Do the students consider the activities challenging enough?		
	c. Do the students show confidence when doing the activities?		
	d. Are the students engaged in the activities?		
	e. Do the students express what they think and feel about the work they are studying?		
	f. Do the students reveal a positive attitude towards their mistakes?		
	g. Do the students react favourably to positive reinforcement words and the acknowledgement of their success?		
	h. Do students connect their experiences to those of the characters in the works they are studying?		

		Yes	No
Behavioural dimension	a. Do the students have good attendance and punctuality?		
	b. Are the students focused during class?		
	c. Do the students demonstrate a disciplined attitude?		
	d. Do the students follow the teacher's instructions?		
	e. Do the students express what they think and feel about the work they are studying?		
	f. Do the students respect each other's interventions?		
	g. Do the students avoid distracting their colleagues in class?		
	h. Do the students avoid taking actions that compromise the flow of the class?		

		Yes	No
Agentive dimension	a. Do the students seem to read beyond what is assigned by the teacher?		
	b. Do the students participate?		
	c. Do the students talk to the teacher about what they enjoy and do not enjoy in class?		
	d. Do the students contribute to deciding aspects related to the activities they are assigned?		
	e. Do the students seek to overcome their difficulties so they can successfully fulfil the activities?		
	f. Do the students show concern with the creativity and originality of their interventions and the products of the activities?		
	g. Do the students enjoy it when they are given the opportunity to decide aspects of the activities they are assigned?		
	h. Do the students show knowledge acquired from personal research and readings done in their free time?		